

Rehabilitation of the Koudane palace structure (Ksour) in Laghouat, Algeria

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to restore an ancient palace called Koudane “ksour” located in the city of Laghouat in Algeria, through the rehabilitation of the structure and ancillary elements in order to enhance and preserve this architectural heritage. The methodology used is based on classic techniques for rehabilitating structural elements and reusing traditional local materials, in line with the vision of sustainable development, which advocates restoration to preserve the historical reading and authenticity of the building classified as historic architectural heritage. The work begins by identifying the different types of damage suffered by the palace, then provides an intervention approach to deal with this damage, proposing the appropriate solution for each type of damage identified. The approach ends with a conclusion on the importance of restoration work on structural elements to enable the rehabilitation of ancient historic buildings.

Keywords: *rehabilitation of the vertical structure, stone palace, architectural heritage in Laghouat*

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development finds its relevance in the preservation of cities' historical heritage. Algeria has realized that its heritage, made up of ancient historic buildings, needs urgent attention. Among its heritage is that of the city of Laghouat, nicknamed “the gateway to the desert”, situated 400 km south of Algiers at an altitude of 750 m, with a surface area of 25,000 km² [1], it was built on the banks of the Oued Mzi, bordered to the south by a pastoral zone extending as far as the Bordj de Thilghemt. Laghouat is one of Algeria's most beautiful cities, combining the Atlas Mountains [2], desert, rocky ridges and palm groves to form a landscape of sublime beauty. It is rich in tourist and historical resources, such as the Madena crater, whose formation dates back more than 3 million years, located at Tilimzen, in the commune of Hassi Delaâ [3], more than 43 archaeological sites dating from the Neolithic and Roman eras have been identified in the communes of El-Ghicha (prehistoric cave paintings), Sidi Makhlof, and Tadjrouna (the Monts Mimouna cave, containing petrified animal remains) [4]. In addition to these historical and tourist relics and monuments, other sites include ancient mosques, the old ksar of El-Hadjadj, the Nedjma and Si El-Haoues squares, and the cupola of Sidi El-Hadj Aïssa. To the north of the wilaya's capital is Aïn Madhi, seat of the general caliphate of the Tidjani brotherhood, which has millions of followers worldwide, particularly in Africa, making it a hub of religious tourism. This town offers a unique architectural mix [5] , including the Ksar de Aïn Madhi, a fortress built in the 12th century [6] , the Palace of Koudrane and Dar Si Ahmed Tidjani (figure 1), where the Frenchwoman Aurélie Picard, wife of one of the Tidjani caliphs in the 19th century, lived [2] [7]. The palace has been considered a museum for tools and

weapons used during the popular resistance to the conquest. Built in 1888, the palace comprises a large residence surrounded by formal gardens and a vast orchard. Unfortunately, it is now abandoned and looks like a ruined carcass, used in places as a vespasienne [8]. Even the furniture and woodwork, made by the most experienced cabinetmaker in the Casbah of Algiers, are in a very advanced state of deterioration [9]. Faced with the seriousness of the situation, we have set ourselves the goal of enhancing, preserving and renovating our heritage by implementing a working methodology that will start with a serious analysis of the state of deterioration of this building (diagnosis), then propose the necessary and effective solutions for the rehabilitation and maintenance of this magnificent palace.

Figure 1: the kourdane palace [author].

II. SCOPE OF WORK

A. *Geographical location*

Aïn Madhi, the cradle of the Tidjania brotherhood, lies on a plain below the Djebel Amour (Saharan Atlas), 66km west of the historic town of Laghouat. The palace of Kourdane, formerly known as Aïn Kourdane and the subject of our study, lies 10km from this commune at an altitude of 987m in the foothills of the Saharan Atlas on the northern side at latitude of $33^{\circ} 50'$ and a longitude of $2^{\circ} 20'$.

B. *Architectural description of the palace*

This sumptuous palace, built in 1888 on a model farm covering an area of 6,000 hectares, was designed by Aurélie Picard, wife of Si Ahmed Ammar Tidjani, the brotherhood's khalif. The palace is a large hexagonal mansion built mainly of stone and decorated with half-French, half-Moorish ceramics, with a large garden and orchard. This architectural heritage comprises a first floor consisting mainly of grain stores, kitchen and dining room. The second floor comprises a succession of four vast rooms with huge windows, entered via a terrace followed by a veranda (fig. 2).

Figure 2: Longitudinal section of the Palace

III. DAMAGE OBSERVED AND SOLUTIONS FOR REPAIRING THE STRUCTURE

It should be pointed out that, whatever the nature of the intervention; it must be carried out gently to respect the history of this heritage.

A. - Foundations and basements

1. Pathologies:

In our case study, there is only one type of traditional foundation: large, relatively hard stones bonded together with lime, sand, cement or even a mixture of these. In reality, these footings under the walls are the result of widening the stone walls at the base, thus forming a rigid system considered as a foundation (fig. 3).

Figure 3: type of foundation used in the palace

It's important to bear in mind that a building's equilibrium can be affected if the foundations or basement are damaged or deteriorated. Particular attention must therefore be paid to these elements.

In the case of the Kourdane palace, no pathology was observed on the foundations, but on the basement, there was deterioration and loosening of the stone bricks or mortar joints in some cases (fig. 4 a.). In other cases, base coatings were either detached and splintered (fig. 4 b), or weathered and cracked (fig. 4 c). In some cases, humidity has been observed on the plaster (fig. 4 d). These pathologies can result from a combination of causes: fatigue, natural ageing of materials, water infiltration, etc.

a) Stone loosening and disjuncting

b) cement plaster splintering
from the substrate

c) Alteration and cracking
of plaster

d) Presence of humidity

Figure 4: Pathologies observed on basements [author].

2. Rehabilitation solutions:

The nature of the work to be carried out depends on the degree of deterioration. Before starting any repair work, at least 15 to 30 cm of the earth or paving stones covering the ring beam should be removed, leaving the ground level below the ring beam. If the deterioration is very slight and superficial (ring beam in good condition), just the damaged areas should be repaired with lime mortar.

If, on the other hand, the foundations have collapsed or the stones have fallen away, the walls must first be supported using props, and then the damaged area must be cleared by cleaning the surface with a brush. We then proceed to rebuild the base with blocks of stone of the same type as those removed, joined together with a sand-lime mortar. Once the base has been rebuilt, a traditional rendering (01 volume of lime plus 02 volumes of sand) is applied, using the traditional finishing techniques of float and smooth, respecting the irregularity of the masonry.

For remedies against dampness, and being aware that it can cause damage on different scales, our solution will lie in an operation aimed at stopping water infiltration, where the paving near the outside walls will be redone by re-adapting a slope from the bottom of the wall, thus avoiding water stagnation. This operation will be accompanied by the removal of anything preventing the natural evaporation of water, then the rendering will be renewed each time there is an alteration, until the phenomenon has completely disappeared. This is known as “sacrificial rendering” [11].

B. Walls, pillars and columns

In the palace under study, the vertical structure is made up of walls, columns and pillars. The load-bearing walls, 50 cm thick on the first floor and 40 cm thick on the first level, are made of limestone bonded with lime and sand mortar. The external faces of the walls are covered by a 10 cm thick solid brick facing (Figure 5). Existing in various forms, the palace's pillars and columns are made of rubble stone or brick (Fig. 6).

Figure 5: Exterior wall [author]

Figure 6(a,b,c): All the pillars and columns in the palace. [Author]

1. Pathologies:

The disorders observed on the walls are those of the second floor, where for the majority of rooms the pathologies summarized in the following points are observed:

- Disjointed: the separation of a wall's stones from one another.
- Punching cracks, through and through cracks, capillary cracks or cracks due to poor load distribution, lack of rigidity (fig. 7), and point load (fig. 8) or load difference between transverse walls (fig. 9).
- Altered, detached plaster or loose earthenware figure (10).

Figure 7 (a, b, c, d and e): cracking due to insufficient stiffness [author]

Figure 8 (a and b): point-load cracking [author]

Figure 9(a, b and c): Cracking resulting from load difference between transverse walls [author]

a) Detachment of earthenware from the substrate

b) deterioration of plaster and paint

Figure 10(a and b): Pathologies observed on renderings [author]

2. Solutions envisaged for the vertical structure:

- **Crack repair**

Prior to any intervention, it is important to identify the origins of the problems and try to find solutions. Depending on the extent of the deterioration, the type of intervention can be proposed.

For shallow and superficial cracks, the first step is to fill them with a sand-lime mortar (compatible with the substrate), stripping carefully around the crack, cleaning well with a brush and then lightly dampening the work surface. Once the cracks have been filled, the plaster is applied.

If the cracks are open, they can be closed by inserting suture-like elements [12], such as metal staples, pieces of stone, etc., between the lips of the crack in the wall (fig. 11). The aim is to regain the lost continuity of the damaged wall, so that stresses can once again be transmitted and distributed evenly throughout the cracked area, i.e., the repair does not interfere with the descent of loads. Alternatively, the masonry on both sides of the crack can be disassembled and reassembled by sealing the opening created during disassembly, using the same traditional techniques and materials. For this method to be effective, the crack must be passive.

Figure 11: Crack repair using staples

- **Wall reconstruction:**

According to the pathologies observed on our site, the majority of walls present partial deterioration, so reconstruction will only concern deteriorated areas, in order to restore the load-bearing capacity of the damaged element. Before undertaking this work, it is important to ensure the stability of the element to be repaired, by shoring up the parts in direct contact with the wall to be restored (Fig.) and then proceeding to remove the damaged stones, while ensuring that their edges are properly cleaned before starting the joints all around the stone to be inserted. To avoid adhesion problems, the damaged areas must be moistened before being restored with new stone bricks, which are then joined together with a sand-lime mortar. For pillars and columns, the same repair techniques will be adopted, depending on the degree of deterioration.

Figure 12: Method for partial repair of a stone brick wall.

If the deterioration of the walls is so extensive that it can lead to total damage, then the situation is dangerous and full reconstruction is justified, as the safety of the building is at risk. Before starting any reconstruction, it is necessary to consolidate the elements supported by the wall by appropriately shoring up the detached wall sections. Next, the wall facings are plumbed to restore the wall's verticality, and reconstruction begins with the installation of new bricks and stones, joined with lime-based mortar. Once the wall has been rebuilt, it is covered with a coating of lime and sand mortar.

For superficial pathologies such as loose plaster, you need to remove the fragile plaster by stripping the wall during the summer, dusting it thoroughly, checking its condition and, if moisture is found, leaving it in the open air for several weeks to

dry thoroughly before carrying out repairs. If cracks exist, treat and close them at least a day before plastering. Moisten and project the sand-lime mortar firmly against the wall. Even out with a trowel, taking care to connect the new surfaces to the same level as the existing old ones. If the wall is an interior wall containing carvings, it should be redone, as there is no shortage of specialists in the area.

To remove loose tiles, start by gently removing them with a scraper, and then carefully clean the surface of the stone wall and the tiles, and move on to applying tile adhesive or glue specially designed for tiles to the surface of the stone wall. Also apply adhesive to the back of the loose tiles and carefully replace them on the stone wall. Press firmly to ensure a good bond. Remove any excess adhesive by wiping immediately with a damp cloth.

C. Floors:

There are two types of floor in the palace under study:

- **vaulted floors:**

This type of floor is found on the second floor, where it consists of a structural layer of metal joists and solid brick vaulted, a filling layer of beaten earth mixed with sand and lime, and a finishing layer of sand and lime. The lower part of the floor is covered by a false ceiling, made from a combination of eave purlin, joists, reed lath and a layer of mixed lime and plaster mortar (fig. 13).

Figure 13: Vaulted floor with false ceiling [author]

- **Traditional flooring:**

Once the load-bearing wall has been built, tree or palm trunks of equal length are laid on top of the wall, with reeds attached to each other and covered with palm leaves. A layer of clay and lime is then laid, which must be thick enough to prevent heat transfer from the outside to the inside (fig.14). On top of this layer, the finishing coat is applied, consisting mainly of terracotta or coloured cement tiles (20 x 20 cm, with floral decorations).

Figure 14: Traditional wooden floor.

1. Floor pathologies:

- **Vaulted floors:**

The following pathologies have been observed in this type of floor:

- Damage and corrosion of metal joists, sometimes leading to rust stains visible on the ceiling (fig.15).
- Cracking where the joists are embedded in the load-bearing wall (fig.16).
- False ceiling detached from the rest of the floor (fig. 17).
- False ceiling plaster detached from wood lath (fig. 18).

a)

b)

Figure 15(a and b): joist corrosion [Author]

a)

b)

Figure 16: Cracking in the recesses [author]

a)

b)

c)

Figure 17((a,b,c,d,e and f): false ceiling detachment [author]

Figure 18: plaster detaching from false ceiling [author]

• **Traditional floorboards:**

The pathologies observed on wooden planks are summarized in the following points:

- Deflection of wooden elements (Fig. 19)
- Wooden beam failure, probably caused either by the application of a high load, undersizing of the beams or their rotting (due to moisture or insect and fungal attack) (Fig.20), sometimes leading to partial collapse of the floor with destruction of the covering (Fig.21).

Figure 19: Deflection of wooden beams
[Author]

Figure 20: Beam failure (due to biotic attack)
[Author]

Figure 21: coating destruction [author]

2. Solutions:

- **Vaulted floors :**

Metal joists superficially affected by corrosion can be treated and passivated. On the other hand, if the joists are heavily corroded (laminated appearance), they must be replaced. Before any repairs are carried out on the floor, it must be perfectly supported with custom-made shoring. Once shored up, the entire upper part of the floor is cleared, the metal joists are cut out, and any spalls and cracks in the load-bearing walls are repaired at the points where the joists were removed, and plastered with mortar, why not cement? The next step is to incorporate the new joists (IPN 160) into the load-bearing walls, ensuring that they are properly sealed. Then the clay bricks (Fig. 22) are laid, using a mobile template clamped under the joists to guide their sealing. The bricks are thoroughly soaked to soften the mortar-filled joints.

Figure 22: Method for rebuilding a vaulted floor [13]

- **Traditional floors:**

For traditional floors, before starting repair work, the first step is to reduce and stop the sources of deformation by reducing bending stresses through the reinforcement or replacement of bent or broken beams. After shoring to prevent the floor from collapsing, the deteriorated beams are carefully removed and replaced by new ones, all of which are chosen from hard palm wood and as straight as possible. Next, the streams and palm fibers are placed, over which a 20 cm layer of earth-lime mortar (plastic consistency, approx. 20% water) is poured. On top of this layer, a 2 cm layer of sand-lime screed is laid, then topped with earthen tiles grouted with lime mortar.

Conclusion

Serious rehabilitation aimed at preserving and enhancing architectural heritage can only succeed if it is based on the results of a compromise between modern and traditional restoration techniques. Adopting the approach used in the appraisal work, the various interventions presented in this work focus on the repair of structural elements. The use of suitable materials with characteristics similar to those of the original materials is recommended to ensure physical-mechanical compatibility, thus preserving the authenticity of the building materials. Also, the use of irreversible materials is to be avoided, as these can adversely affect the structural behaviour of stone constructions.

In order to preserve a historic heritage, owners should be encouraged to conserve rather than rebuild, so as to preserve the historical interpretation and authenticity of the building.

References

- [1] Données du recensement général de la population et de l'habitat de 2008 sur le site de ONS, " Wilaya de Laghouat : répartition de la population résidente des ménages ordinaires et collectifs, selon la commune de résidence et la dispersion [archive]",".
- [2] T.Bourzgue, Y. Daikh, " Méthodes de réhabilitation du patrimoine ancien de la ville de Laghouat," ; Thèse de Master, université Eloued Algérie , 2013
- [3] A.Nedjari, M. Chettih, "Le Cratere De Talemzane (maadna, Hassi Delaa, Laghouat) : Impact de meteorite ou affaissement d'un Diapir," Bulletin du Service Géologique de l'Algérie, Volume 32, Numéro 1, Pages 63-92,2023:
- [4] R. Perret, "Une carte des gravures rupestres et des peintures à l'ocre de l'Afrique du Nord," Journal des Africanistes , 1937.
- [5] J. Yves Thorignac, " Le village de Ain Madhi,". Info 560 Ain Madhi.
- [6] M.T. Serchine, " L'architecture Ksourienne ," Thèse de master en architecture, université Blida 1 Algérie , 2022.
- [7] N.Bourebi, " L'architecture palatine monographie palais Kourdane,"Thèse de Master en architecture, université Blida 1 Algérie, 2015.
- [8] A. Djabouabdallah, I. Larbi Daouadji, "Mise en valeur du Ksar d'Ain Madhi par le tourisme spirituel essai sur les espaces sacré," Thèse de Master en Architecture et urbanisme. Université Abdelhamid Ibn Badis de Mostaganem Algérie, 2018.
- [9] I. Fentazi, " Le ménagement des opérations de conservations du patrimoine bâti en Algérie dans un contexte évènementiel," Thèse de doctorat. université Salah Boubnider Constantine 3 Algérie, 2021
- [10] Le journal le soir, "Laghouat: programme de classification et de restauration de sites archéologiques," Algérie, 2019.
- [11] J. Jeannet et al, "Le bâti ancien: analyse, pathologie, remède," Livre, Ed. Pisé, terre d'avenir, France ,1996.
- [12] C. Diaz Gómez, " La réhabilitation des éléments structuraux de l'architecture traditionnelle méditerranéenne," Méthode Réhabimed, 2005.
- [13] S.A.S. WALRAVENS, "Eco-Maçonnerie et taille de pierres," Hérault 34, France.